

MARKETING ANALYSIS OF THE MARKET FOR CARDIOTONIC DRUGS

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Relevance: Cardiotonics are a group of medications used to enhance the function of the heart muscle, improve its contractile ability, and treat heart failure. This group includes a significant number of drugs containing various active ingredients and other mechanisms of action[2].

Purpose of the study: to analyze the assortment of cardiotoxic drugs for the period of 2019-2023 based on content analysis and DRUG AUDIT data to study their position in the pharmaceutical market[1].

Materials and methods: the analysis utilized the "State Register of Medicines, Medical Devices, and Medical Equipment Permitted for Use in Medical Practice in the Republic of Uzbekistan" for the period of 2019-2023, the Essential Medicines List of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and DRUG AUDIT data.

Results: according to the August 31, 2023 Essential Medicines List of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in the 11th section (cardiovascular), drugs containing digoxin as the main active ingredient are listed as cardiotoxic agents. According to the 27th edition of the "State Register of Medicines, Medical Devices, and Medical Equipment Permitted for Use in Medical Practice in the Republic of Uzbekistan" for 2023, a total of 18 cardiotoxic drugs have been registered in Uzbekistan. Of these drugs, 14 (78%) are produced by local manufacturers, 3 (16.5%) by foreign manufacturers, and 1 (5.5%) by manufacturers from CIS countries. In 2019-2020, the number of cardiotoxic drugs registered by local manufacturers increased, while the share of cardiotoxic drugs produced by CIS and foreign manufacturers remained almost unchanged.

The market for cardiotoxic drugs during 2018-2022 was analyzed based on DRUG AUDIT data. The analysis showed that the growth of cardiotoxic drugs in the pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan slightly decreased in 2018-2019, but after 2020, the market share of cardiotoxic drugs increased yearly, and proportionally, the production of cardiotoxic drugs by local manufacturers also increased.

Conclusions: Although cardiotoxic drugs produced by foreign manufacturers have demonstrated a diversity in drug forms in the local market, the share of cardiotoxic drugs produced by local pharmaceutical companies is

increasing yearly. Since 2018, the number of cardiotoxic drugs produced by local manufacturers has increased, and at the same time, the share of drugs imported from foreign countries and CIS states has also slightly increased. Furthermore, it is considered appropriate to produce certain dosage forms (injectable and infusion solutions, capsules) of cardiotoxic drugs available in the local market and those imported from abroad. Therefore, it is highly relevant to introduce new pharmacological groups and new dosage forms of cardiotoxic drugs into production by local pharmaceutical companies.

References:

1. Sarvarova, D. M., Madatova, N. A., Yunuskhodzhaeva, N. A., Iminova, I. M. Study Of The Assortment Of Antioxidant And Hemostatic Medicines Registered In The Republic of Uzbekistan. Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results, 2023, pp. 1028-1033.
2. Мадатова Н. Получение лекарственной формы на основе биологически активных веществ растения пустырник //Каталог авторефератов. – 2008. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 1-22.
3. Muxutdinovna R. N., Abdugaffarovna M. N. O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA QAYD ETILGAN BIOLOGIK FAOL QO'SHIMCHALAR ASSORTIMENT TAHLILI //Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 1-2. – С. 191-197

